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Research Paper

Diagnostic method of solar thermal system based on the short time on-line measurements

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HIGHLIGHTS

- New short-time on-line diagnostics method of a solar heating system.
- Short time on-line measurements for determination of static and dynamic properties.
- Analysis of static and dynamic properties at different volumetric flow rates.
- Impact analysis of flow rate on characteristic parameters of collector.

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the method of a solar heating system diagnostics allowing determination of the following coefficients in operating conditions: heat loss coefficient U_{LK} , collector efficiency factor F' and heat removal factor F_R related to the collector static properties, effective heat capacity $(mc)_e$ and time-constant T_e related to the collector dynamic properties. The proposed method is based on a comparison of two models: analytical and numerical. The analytical model was developed based on the collector energy balance and that combining characteristic parameters. The numerical model was developed based on the recorded operating data of the medium inlet and outlet temperature, and solar irradiance. The condition necessary to apply this method covers constant volume flow rate of the medium in the system during the experiment.

1. Introduction

In the moderate climate zone, the available solar radiation resources do not cover the heat demand. Therefore, solar heating systems are used to support the operation of heat sources that consume conventional energy carriers and renewable energy – heat pumps in the so called hybrid power supply systems. The main function of solar heating system in hybrid power supply system is to reduce the consumption of conventional energy carriers and thereby reduce the greenhouse gases emissions and find an alternative heat supply solution [1,2]. Large-scale simulation tests as well as field tests [3–6] focusing on solar systems combined with other heat sources in the hybrid power supply systems are currently being conducted in order to assess efficient energy use.

1.1. Problem definition

The consumption of a conventional carrier mainly depends on the correct design of the solar heating system and the control algorithm for

both the solar heating system operation and the entire hybrid system. In operating conditions, as a result of stochastic disturbances (momentary variability of solar irradiance, hot water consumption from the system, fluctuations of ambient temperature and medium inlet temperature), the solar segment is in transient states [7,8]. Therefore, it is important to develop an appropriate control algorithm for the solar segment operation, which significantly determines the achieved system capacity [9–11]. The accomplishment of this objective requires, first of all, determination of dynamic properties of the solar segment in operating conditions [12] and values of parameters determining its static properties. In practice, the solar segment is designed based on the efficiency characteristics of a single collector, determined during experiments under indoor or outdoor conditions [13], based on standard tests according to ISO 9806 standard [14]. In the assessment of the collector static properties, the efficiency characteristics are considered a quality parameter. The collector efficiency characteristics according to the standard may be determined using two methods: steady state method that was treated as the main method in the Ashrae standard [15], EN

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Nomenclature

A_c	aperture area [m ²]
c_p	medium specific heat [J/kgK]
$e(t)$	non-measurable disturbance in discrete step t (white noise)
F'	collector efficiency factor
F_R	heat removal factor
$G(s)$	operator transmittance
I	solar irradiance [W/m ²]
k_p	gain coefficient
\dot{m}	medium flow rate [l/s]
$(mc)_e$	effective heat capacity [J/K]
n_k	delay between the output and input signals (number of samples)
P_{in}	supplied power [W]
P_{out}	output power [W]

s	variable for the Laplace transform
T	temperature [°C]
t	time [s]
T_c	time-constant [s]
$u(t)$	observation of the object input in discrete step t
U_{LK}	overall collector heat loss coefficient [W/m ² K]
y	measured signal
$y(t)$	observation of the object output in discrete step t
z	discrete operator

List of indices

amb	ambient
in	inlet
K	collector
out	outlet

12975-2 standard [16] and quasi dynamic method (QDT) developed by Amer [17], enabling the collector testing in transient states. It should be emphasized that in both methods, the efficiency characteristics and the substitute time-constant reflecting dynamic properties are determined for a collector not heat loaded with a domestic hot water storage tank (DHW). In practice, solar heating systems are composed of several collectors or even several dozen collectors interconnected in parallel and heat loaded with the tank (DHW). The value of heat load of the collectors, volume flow rate in the system and the operating conditions have a significant impact on static and dynamic properties of a single collector, which translates into efficiency and capacity of the entire system, and thus the system operating costs [18]. The increase in the solar system operation capacity requires designing of a control system specific for each solar system. To this end, it is necessary to know the dynamic properties of the solar segment in time domain and analysis of their variability as a function of working medium flow rate.

1.2. Literature review

Static and dynamic properties of collector depend on design parameters and they have significant impact on solar collector efficiency. The collector static and dynamic properties and solar system efficiency can be determined at the design stage using, for example, methods that are based on analog models.

Amrizal et al. [19] presented the model of collector that enables transient states to be analyzed. The proposed model in form of linear differential equation with respect to input parameters enables thermal efficiency of collector to be predicted for different weather conditions. Buzás et al. [20] developed the model of collector in form of transfer function that enables dynamic properties to be analyzed. The model was used for designing control system of solar installation. Based on the results of simulation tests, it was showed that the analysis of collector dynamic properties and application of proper control system enable efficiency of solar installation to increase. Deng et al. [21] analyzed second-order function model of collector based on heat removal factor F_R . Factors of collector model were determined using the method of least squares. The model was verified based on experimental data [22]. Deng et al. [23] presented the simple model of collector based on the piston flow concept. They used nonlinear least squares method in order to determine collector parameters. The model enables dynamic behavior of the collector outlet temperature to be predicted. The results of the prediction are satisfactory except for some specific cases, for example, when solar irradiance changes rapidly. Zhang et al. [24] developed the physical model of collector based on finite volume method that can optimize collector regarding its structure. Based on the results, it was concluded that increase of instantaneous efficiency mostly

depends on heat pipe diameter, evaporator length, absorber plate thickness and inclination angle of collector. Hu et al. [25] developed and verified the dynamic model of collector that can optimize collector structure in order to increase its efficiency. Simonetti et al. [26] developed the dynamic model of hybrid collector that enables transient states to be analyzed. The model was built using a control volume approach. The collector is divided into small elemental volumes where energy equation is solved using a bi-dimensional finite difference method. The model was verified and enables short and long-term energy-based analysis of collector to be conducted. Chochowski et al. [27] overviewed the models that can analyze thermal states of collector using equivalent thermal network (ETN). Based on the review, they proposed the optimum ETN model of collector composed of three homogeneous bodies: glass cover, absorber and working medium, and presented the algorithm for calculating the values of ETN factors. Aleksiejuk et al. [28] developed the analog model of collector based on ETN. This model uses design and operating parameters, which enables static and dynamic properties of collector to be determined at the design stage. The ETN model was verified using digital model determined by experiment based on the parametric identification method. Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al. [29] applied ETN to simulate solar system operation. The model was made for solar installation composed of 50 m² of collectors. The obtained transient states were compared to thermal inertia under quasi-dynamic conditions proposed in EN-12975: 2006 standard. Ayompe et al. [30] applied TRNSYS model to simulate operation of solar heating system composed of two flat-plate collectors and heat pipe collector. The model was verified, which helped to estimate errors between actual and simulated outlet temperature. Based on the results obtained after one year of measurements, system efficiency was calculated and it was 37.8% [31]. Guarracino et al. [32] analyzed the dynamic model of PVT collector that enables annual production of domestic hot water and electrical energy to be evaluated. The analysis can be conducted for steady states as well as for transient states. Based on the results, it was concluded that obtained efficiencies of the system depend on dynamic properties of the system and proper selection of control parameters (pump operation, differential thermostat controller, flow rate, etc.) in response to the varying weather conditions.

It should be noted that the collector static and dynamic properties in operating conditions may differ from those determined during standard tests or using analytical methods at the design stage. Moreover, having the information of static and dynamic properties of a single collector, it is difficult to refer to static and dynamic properties of the entire solar system. Therefore, it is very important to determine static and dynamic properties of the solar system in operating conditions. This paper presents the diagnostics method of solar system segment in operating conditions.

2. Theoretical basis of the method

The proposed method of the solar heating system diagnostics enables determination, in operating conditions, of system parameter values specifying its static parameters, i.a.: heat loss coefficient U_{LK} , collector efficiency factor F' , heat removal factor F_R , and heat capacity $(mc)_{eK}$ having an impact on the collector dynamic properties. The method is based on two equivalent models: one developed based on the operating data using the Blackbox identification method, and the other one developed based on energy balance combining the listed collector characteristic parameters [33]. The comparison of both models allows for determination of the characteristic parameter values of the diagnosed solar system. The only requirement consists in the maintenance of a constant medium flow rate in the system during the experiment.

The Blackbox method, similarly to artificial neuron networks, was already used for modeling and diagnosing solar systems [34–36]. In document [34], the solar segment was regarded as a double-input and single-input object, and solar irradiance per the absorber area unit and ambient temperature were adopted as input signals, whereas the medium outlet temperature was adopted as the output signal. Time series from four days were used for the estimation of the model coefficients, and the model structure is quite complicated. The model regards the solar collector as a body composed of two homogeneous bodies, identifying in the model the medium and absorber heat capacity. The model includes the working medium weight in the solar system, but it does not include the volume flow rate. Based on this model, it is possible to determine the efficiency characteristics of the modeled collector and effective power output obtained from the collector in steady state, whereas the collector dynamic properties were omitted.

The proposed diagnostics method enables determination of both static and dynamic properties of the solar segment. To diagnose the collector segment, it is necessary to:

- develop analytical model based on the energy balance, combining the characteristic parameters (aperture area $-A_c$, heat removal factor $-F_R$, collector efficiency factor $-F'$, effective heat capacity $-(mc)_{eK}$, heat loss coefficient U_{LK}),
- develop an equivalent a numerical model based on the recorded input and output signals for constant medium flow rate in the solar system with the use of the Blackbox identification method,
- next, compare both models and determine the values of parameters characterizing static and dynamic properties of the diagnosed collector segment.

2.1. The collector analytical model was developed based on energy balance

Based on the equation developed by Hottel Willier and Bliss (HWB) [37], the transient state of the flat-plate collector can be recorded using differential Eq. (1).

$$\frac{dT_{out}(t)}{dt} = \frac{P_{in}(t) - P_{out}(t)}{(mc)_e} \quad (1)$$

Solar radiation power absorbed by the collector absorber is defined using relation (2), combining solar irradiance, collector aperture area and heat removal factor F_R .

$$P(t) = I(s) \cdot A_c \cdot F_R [W] \quad (2)$$

Power output from the collector is expressed by relation (3), combining the heat flow of the working medium to the storage tank and heat losses from the collector.

$$P_{out} = \dot{m}c_p \cdot (T_{out} - T_{in}) + U_{LK} \cdot (T_{in} - T_{amb}) \quad (3)$$

Assuming that in steady state the solar radiation energy is equal to power output from the collector, the transient state of the output temperature can be described using relation (4).

$$\frac{dT_{out}(t)}{dt} = \frac{I(t) \cdot A_c \cdot F_R - \dot{m}c_p \cdot (T_{out}(t) - T_{in}(t)) - U_{LK} \cdot (T_{in}(t) - T_{amb}(t))}{(mc)_{eK}} \quad (4)$$

By multiplying the particular expressions in Eq. (4) and organizing them according to sides, we obtain an analytical model of collector batteries in transient state (5).

$$\frac{(mc)_{eK}}{\dot{m}c_p} \frac{dT_{out}(t)}{dt} + T_{out}(t) = \frac{A_c \cdot F_R}{\dot{m}c_p} \cdot I(t) + \frac{(\dot{m}c_p - U_{LK})}{\dot{m}c_p} \cdot T_{in}(t) + \frac{U_{LK}}{\dot{m}c_p} \cdot T_{amb}(t) \quad (5)$$

Eq. (5) using Laplace transform of time domain to complex variable domain, we obtain Eq. (6).

$$T_{out}(s) = \underbrace{\frac{\frac{A_c \cdot F_R}{\dot{m}c_p}}{\left(\frac{(mc)_{eK}}{\dot{m}c_p}\right)s + 1}}_{\text{Main path}} \cdot I(s) + \underbrace{\frac{\frac{(\dot{m}c_p - U_{LK})}{\dot{m}c_p}}{\left(\frac{(mc)_{eK}}{\dot{m}c_p}\right)s + 1}}_{\text{Disturbance path I}} \cdot T_{in}(s) + \underbrace{\frac{\frac{U_{LK}}{\dot{m}c_p}}{\left(\frac{(mc)_{eK}}{\dot{m}c_p}\right)s + 1}}_{\text{Disturbance path II}} \cdot T_{amb}(s) \quad (6)$$

Considering the fact that the parametric model of the solar segment will be developed based on operating data that are correlated with ambient temperature, the second disturbance path in relation (6) can be omitted. In such case, the collector analytical model describing transient state is simplified to the form 7, which can be presented using a block diagram (Fig. 1).

$$T_{out}(s) = \frac{\frac{A_c \cdot F_R}{\dot{m}c_p}}{\left(\frac{(mc)_{eK}}{\dot{m}c_p}\right)s + 1} \cdot I(s) + \frac{\frac{(\dot{m}c_p - U_{LK})}{\dot{m}c_p}}{\left(\frac{(mc)_{eK}}{\dot{m}c_p}\right)s + 1} \cdot T_{in}(s) \quad (7)$$

It should be noticed that the main path and disturbance path transmittance is the transmittance specific for the first order inert object described with general operator transmittance 8.

$$G(s) = \frac{y(s)}{u(s)} = \frac{kp}{T_C(s) + 1} = \frac{kp}{T_C} \cdot \frac{1}{s + \frac{1}{T_C}} \quad (8)$$

The gain coefficient of the main path kp_1 can be calculated based on relation (9), and the disturbance path kp_2 based on relation (10). It should be noted that both paths of the model have a common characteristic equation (transmittance denominator), in which time-constant T_z can be calculated based on relation (11).

$$kp_1 = \frac{A_c \cdot F_R}{\dot{m}c_p} \quad (9)$$

$$kp_2 = \frac{\dot{m}c_p - U_L}{\dot{m}c_p} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 1. The block diagram of the solar segment model developed based on energy balance for transient state.

$$T_C = \frac{(mc)_e}{\dot{m}c_p} \tag{11}$$

2.2. The parametric collector model developed based on the operating data with the use of the Blackbox identification method

Two paths of the solar segment can be identified in the analytical model: the main path and the disturbance path. The equivalent parametric model also has two identical paths. Therefore, it will be possible to compare both models and determine the parameters that are characteristic for the diagnosed system.

The model in the form of general differential equations (12), referred to as the Box Jenkins model [38], is the main model in parametric identification. As part of this model structure, any finite system of fixed disturbances with measurable spectral concentration may be described,

$$A(z)y(t) = \frac{B(z)}{F(z)}u(t - n_k) + \frac{C(z)}{D(z)}e(t) \tag{12}$$

where A(z), B(z), C(z), D(z), F(z) are matrix polynomials with dimensions determined using appropriate formulas.

$$\begin{aligned} A(z) &= 1 + a_1z^{-1} + a_2z^{-2} + \dots + a_nz^{-na} \\ B(z) &= b_0 + b_1z^{-1} + b_2z^{-2} + \dots + b_nz^{-nb} \\ C(z) &= 1 + c_1z^{-1} + c_2z^{-2} + \dots + c_nz^{-nc} \\ D(z) &= 1 + d_1z^{-1} + d_2z^{-2} + \dots + d_nz^{-nd} \\ F(z) &= 1 + f_1z^{-1} + f_2z^{-2} + \dots + f_nz^{-nd} \end{aligned}$$

Tests performed by the authors show that the static and dynamic properties of solar heating systems can be successfully modeled, with appropriate accuracy of > 95%, using a simplification of structure 12 to form 13.

$$A(z)y(t) = B(z)u(t - n_k) + e(t) \tag{13}$$

By using the Tustin transform (14) for the given sampling time “t” of continuous analog signals, the differential equation system transformed to discrete transmittance G(z) (15) may be transformed to general operator transmittance G(s) (16), enabling analysis of static and dynamic properties of the solar system.

$$s = \frac{1}{t} \cdot \ln(z) = \frac{1}{t} \left[(z - 1) - \frac{(z - 1)^2}{2} - \dots \right] \rightarrow s = \frac{1}{t}(z - 1) \tag{14}$$

$$G(z) = \frac{a_nz^{-na} - \dots - a_2z^{-2} - a_1z^{-1} - 1}{1 - b_1z^{-1} - b_2z^{-2} - \dots - b_nz^{-nb}} \tag{15}$$

$$G(s) = \frac{kp_1}{T_{C1}s + 1} \cdot \frac{kp_2}{T_{C2}s + 1} \cdot \dots \cdot \frac{kp_n}{T_{Cn}s + 1} \tag{16}$$

The mathematical model of the system may be presented using a block diagram (Fig. 2), which shows that the solar segment model is composed of two paths: the main path and the disturbance path. The path related to solar irradiance and medium output temperature, described by operator transmittance G₁(s) (17), should be adopted as the main path. The path related to input and output temperature, described by operator transmittance G₂(s) (18), should be adopted as the disturbance path. Such form of the model of the flat-plate solar collector segment enables assessment of the impact of solar irradiance and medium input temperature on the medium output temperature from the solar segment. Thus, it is possible to determine the dynamic properties of the modeled collector batteries in operating conditions. When analyzing the gain coefficients of both paths of the collector segment model, it is also possible to analyze the collector static properties as well.

$$G_1(s) = \frac{T_{out}(s)}{I(s)} = \frac{kp_1}{T_C(s) + 1} \tag{17}$$

$$G_2(s) = \frac{T_{out}}{T_{in}} = \frac{kp_2}{T_C(s) + 1} \tag{18}$$

Since the main path is connected with the disturbance path by means of the summation node, the transient state of output temperature can be calculated using the relation as in (19).

$$T_{out}(s) = G_1(s) \cdot I(s) + G_2(s) \cdot T_{in}(s) \tag{19}$$

When substituting relation (19) with the particular constituents of the main path 17, and the disturbance path 18, we obtain Eq. (20).

$$T_{out}(s) = \frac{kp_1}{T_C(s) + 1} \cdot I(s) + \frac{kp_2}{T_C(s) + 1} \cdot T_{in}(s) \tag{20}$$

The presented analysis shows that relation (7) developed based on energy balance is equivalent to relation (20) obtained as a result of the conducted parametric identification. When comparing both models (analytical and parametric), with the known value of: medium specific heat c_p, flow rate \dot{m} and collector(s) aperture area A_C, it is possible to determine the sought collector(s) characteristic parameters: effective heat capacity (mc)_e, heat loss coefficient U_{LK}, heat removal factor F_R and substitute time-constant T_z in operating conditions.

3. Description of the test stand

The method possibilities will be presented based on an example of a solar heating system composed of two flat-plate collectors connected in parallel and heat loaded with a 100 dm³ storage tank (Fig. 3).

The data sheet operating parameters of the collectors are presented in Table 1. According to the data sheet, the parameter values were determined for the flow rate of 0.02 kg/m² of the collector aperture area. Due to the fact that glycol is the working medium in the collectors, thermal energy is exchanged with the hot water storage tank using the pipe coil heat exchanger located inside the tank. The control algorithm was implemented in the PLC connected using TCPiP with a PC with the implemented SCADA type program, that enables visualization of energy conversion process and archiving of measuring data. For the measurement of the medium input and output temperature of each collector, thermal resistant PT1000 sensors in a four-wire arrangement were used. The sensors were placed in capillary tubes. The medium flow was forced using a variable speed pump. A flow meter was used to measure the medium flow rate in the solar system. The stand advantage consists in the possibility to perform operating experiments with the assumed initial conditions, i.a.: initial temperature in the DHW storage tank, initial medium inlet temperature in the solar system and any medium flow rate within the circulating pump capacity range (0–100%). The possibility of changing the collector battery size (1 or 2 collectors) and the possibility of changing the heat load (capacity of the DHW storage tank) are also an advantage.

4. Analysis of dynamic properties of a solar system in time domain

The diagnostics of a solar system will be presented based on the example of operating data shown in Fig. 4. It should be noted that during the system operation, weather conditions were variable. The

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the solar collector model.

Fig. 3. Test stand.

initial temperature in the domestic hot water storage tank amounted to 20.4 °C, whereas the final temperature amounted to 69.2 °C. To enable reference to data sheet parameters, the experiment was conducted for the medium flow rate in the system of 0.08 kg/s, which caused that in the case of parallel connection of collectors, the flow rate per one square meter of the collector aperture area amounted to 0.02 kg/s. Propylene glycol was used as the working medium, whose specific heat amounted to $c_p = 3580$ [J/kgK].

The *System Identification Toolbox* of the Matlab package was used to prepare the solar segment parametric model. As a result of the identification process based on the operating data, a model was developed in the form of a system of differential equations (21), that was validated by a comparison of the simulated outlet temperature values with the actual ones (Fig. 5).

$$\begin{aligned} A(z) &= 1 - 0.9943z - 1 \\ B1(z) &= 6.116e - 5z - 1 \\ B2(z) &= 0.005267z - 1 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

The *Best Fits* coefficient calculated based on relation (22) was equal to 97.74%

$$BestFits = 100 \cdot \frac{(1 - |y_m - y|)}{|y - y_s|} \quad (22)$$

The system of differential equations (21) should be recorded in the form of discrete transmittance (23, 24) and next should be transformed using the Tustin transform (3) to operator transmittance, describing the main path (25) and disturbance path (26) properties.

$$G_1(z) = \frac{6.11e^{-5}z^{-1}}{1 - 0.9943z^{-1}} \quad (23)$$

$$G_2(z) = \frac{0.005267z^{-1}}{1 - 0.9943z^{-1}} \quad (24)$$

The determined operator transmittance $G_1(s)$ and $G_2(s)$ correspond to the properties of a first order inert object of general form 5. Value of the main path gain coefficient $kp_1 = 0.0108$, whereas the substitute time-constant determined as 0.632 of steady state amounts to $T_z = 178.36$ s. Value of the disturbance path gain coefficient $kp_2 = 0.92$, whereas the substitute time-constant identical as in the case of the main path amounts to $T_z = 178.36$ s.

Table 1
Data sheet parameters of a flat-plate solar collector.

Effective heat capacity [kJ/m ² K]	Heat loss coefficient [W/m ² K]	Substitute time-constant [s]	Collector area [m ²]	Aperture area [m ²]	Absorber material	Glass thickness [mm]
5.85	3.56	69	2.3	2.0	Copper Covered with a selective coating	3.2

$$G_1(s) = \frac{y_1(s)}{u_1(s)} = \frac{6.133e^{-5}}{s + 0.0568} = \frac{0.0108}{178.36s + 1} \quad (25)$$

$$G_2(s) = \frac{y_2(s)}{u_2(s)} = \frac{0.005282}{s + 0.00568} = \frac{0.92}{178.36s + 1} \quad (26)$$

Having the operator transmittance (25, 26), describing dynamic properties of the individual model paths for known flow rate and specific heat of the medium, and by transforming relations (9, 10, 11), it is possible to determine characteristic parameters of the modeled segment: F_R , U_{LK} and $(mc)_{eK}$, and of a single collector. The values of the particular characteristic parameters of a single collector are presented in Table 2. The presented analysis shows that the collector characteristic parameters determined based on the standard tests conducted in no-load state (without heat load due to the domestic hot water storage tank) are different that the collector parameters in operating conditions, in which the collector operates under heat load.

The division of the collector model into two independent paths (the main and the disturbance paths) enables analysis of the impact of the variability and value of solar irradiance as well as medium inlet temperature on medium outlet temperature variations. Having operator transmittance of the main path (25) and the disturbance path (26), it is possible to determine the response of the model particular paths on step input, by substituting $u(s) = \frac{1}{s}$ (27).

$$y(s) = \frac{kp}{T_c s + 1} \cdot u(s) = \frac{kp}{s(T_c s + 1)} = \frac{kp}{T_c} \cdot \frac{1}{s\left(s + \frac{1}{T_c}\right)} \quad (27)$$

Using the inverse Laplace transform, Eq. (27) of the complex variable domain should be transformed to general time domain 28.

$$y(t) = L^{-1}[y(s)] = \frac{kp}{T_c} \cdot T_c \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{T_c}}\right) = kp \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{T_c}}\right) \quad (28)$$

The transient state of the solar segment main path can be determined using relation (29), whereas that of the disturbance path using relation (30).

$$y_1(t) = 0.0108 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{178.36}}\right) \quad (29)$$

$$y_2(t) = 0.92 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{178.36}}\right) \quad (30)$$

The presented block diagram (Fig. 1, Fig. 2) shows that the step response of the modeled solar segment is the sum of the transient state history of the particular model paths. To determine it, it is necessary to substitute the particular transmittance to relation (7) and determine the original function by introducing the input with amplitude $u(t) = 1$ as input signals. The transient state of the solar segment output temperature calculated based on relation (31) for zero initial conditions is presented in Fig. 6. By transforming operator transmittance into differential equations, it is also possible to determine step response of the particular model paths and the entire solar segment for any medium inlet temperature and solar irradiance.

$$T_{out}(t) = 0.0108 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{178.36}}\right) + 0.92 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{178.36}}\right) \quad (31)$$

Having operating data recorded during several days of the system operation, it is possible to analyze the correlation of different factors, i.e., the medium volume flow rate and the solar segment operating parameters.

Fig. 4. Solar irradiance and medium temperature values during the experiment.

An exemplary analysis of the volume flow rate impact on the solar segment static properties is presented based on the data recorded during eighteen days of the system operation. Due to the fact that the collectors were interconnected in the battery in parallel, assuming identical flow resistance, the medium volume flow through the collector is equal to 50% of the volume flow in the entire system. Knowing

the flow rate through a single collector, it is possible to relate to the collector operating parameters determined in accordance with the ISO 9806 standard. Six experiments were performed for each of the three flow rate values of the working medium: minimum flow rate of 2.28 [l/min] - (0.019 [l/(s)] through one collector) corresponding to zero pump control, maximum flow rate of 7.68 [l/min] - (0.064 [l/(s)] through one

Fig. 5. Comparison of the simulated outlet temperature values with the actual ones.

Table 2
Comparison of the collector parameters in operating conditions with the data sheet parameters.

Collector operating parameters	$Kp_{G1(s)}$ [-]	$Kp_{G2(s)}$ [-]	T_c [s]	F_R [-]	U_{Lk} [W/m ² K]	$(mc)_{ek}$ [kJ/m ² K]
Operating conditions	0.0108	0.92	181.63	0.79	5.02	12.77
Data sheet	–	–	69	–	3.56	5.85

collector] corresponding to full (100%) pump control and 5.4 [l/min] - 0.045 [l/s] through one collector] corresponding to 50% of the circulating pump control.

Figs. 7 and 8 show the impact of the circulating pump capacity on gain coefficients of the main and disturbance paths. They show that along with the increase in the circulating pump capacity, the gain coefficient kp_1 of the main path decreases, and the gain coefficient kp_2 of the disturbance path increases.

This means that in case of higher volume flow rates of the medium, the medium inlet temperature has more significant impact on the collector battery operation. Changes in the gain coefficients of both model paths kp_1 , kp_2 as a function of the circulating pump capacity are non-linear. In the analyzed case, they can be estimated using polynomial functions 32 and 33 for determination coefficients of $R^2 = 0.97$ and $R^2 = 0.95$, respectively. The distribution of residues confirms the repeatability of the obtained results.

$$kp_1 = 8.4 \cdot \dot{m}^2 - 1 \cdot \dot{m} + 0.04 \tag{32}$$

$$kp_2 = -33 \cdot \dot{m}^2 + 4.3 \cdot \dot{m} + 0.81 \tag{33}$$

Fig. 9 shows the relation between the main path gain coefficient kp_1 and the disturbance path gain coefficient kp_2 . The coefficients are linearly dependent. This relation for the analyzed solar system can be described using Eq. (34) for determination coefficient $R^2 = 0.95$.

$$kp_2 = -4.475 \cdot kp_1 + 0.982 \tag{34}$$

Having Eqs. (9) and (10) as well as 25 and 26 for any circulating pump capacity within the operating range, i.e.: 2.28 [l/min] -7.68 [l/min], it is possible to determine the heat loss coefficient U_{Lk} and the heat removal factor F_R . In addition, having the heat removal factor F_R and using relation (35), it is possible to determine the collector efficiency factor F' . Thus, families of the system efficiency characteristics can be developed, depending on the circulating pump capacity, which allows for determination of the medium volume flow rate impact on the system efficiency, depending on the temperature level in the domestic

hot water storage tank.

$$F_R = \frac{\dot{m}c_p}{A_c U_L} \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{A_c U_L F'}{\dot{m}c_p}\right) \right] \tag{35}$$

Fig. 10 shows the relation of the collector efficiency factor F' and the heat removal factor F_R as a function of circulating pump capacity for the diagnosed system. The figure indicates that the initial increase in the circulating pump capacity causes an increase in the coefficient values. In the case of factor F_R from 0.66 for the flow rate of 0.019 [l/s] to 0.772 corresponding to the flow rate of 0.029 [l/s]. In the case of factor F' from 0.68 for the flow rate of 0.016 [l/s] to 0.801 corresponding to the flow rate of 0.029 [l/s]. Further increase in the pump capacity to 0.05 [l/s] results in a decrease in the factor values in the case of factor F_R to 0.71 and in the case of factor F' to 0.726. By increasing the circulating pump capacity to the maximum value of 0.064 [l/s], values of both factors increase to $F_R = 0.769$, $F' = 0.785$, respectively. The obtained results are similar to the results presented in document [39], whereas the results presented in document [39] were based on theoretical considerations.

The change in the circulating pump capacity has also an impact on the heat loss coefficient U_{Lk} (Fig. 11). By increasing the circulating pump capacity in the analyzed case from minimum value of 0.019 [l/s], the heat loss coefficient U_{Lk} increases non-linearly from 3.85 [W/m²K] to 6.29 [W/m²K], corresponding to the maximum circulating pump capacity of 0.064 [l/s].

Fig. 12 shows the comparison of the collector efficiency characteristics determined in accordance with the ISO 9806 standard with the characteristics of the collector heat loaded with the storage tank for three capacity values of the circulating pump: minimum capacity of 0.019 [l/s], maximum capacity of 0.064 [l/s] and intermediate capacity of 0.045 [l/s].

Both the collector heat load and the changed circulating pump capacity has an impact on the collector operating parameters. The collector battery achieves the lowest zero-loss efficiency of 0.63 at the

Fig. 6. Step response of the modeled solar segment.

Fig. 7. Impact of the circulating pump capacity on the gain coefficient of the disturbance path $R^2 = 0.97$.

Fig. 8. Impact of the circulating pump capacity on the gain coefficient of the main path.

minimum flow rate. The highest zero-loss efficiency of 0.73 is achieved by the collector battery at the maximum flow rate. At the minimum flow rate, the heat loss coefficient U_{LK} is the lowest and it equals to 4.22 [W/m²K], and at the maximum flow rate it is the highest and amounts to 4.82 [W/m²K]. In consequence, the collector battery efficiency at higher medium temperature is achieved for lower flow rate. This

confirms the previous tests of the authors included in the document [40]. The presented analysis shows that the medium temperature should be one of the determinants according to which the solar system operation should be controlled. In the case of the analyzed system, the efficiency characteristics can be accordingly described with relations

Fig. 9. Relation of the main path gain coefficient as a function of the disturbance path coefficient.

Fig. 10. Impact of the circulating pump capacity on F_R and F' values.

$$\eta = 0.63 - 4.22T_m - 1.35T_m^2 \tag{36}$$

$$\eta = 0.68 - 4.79T_m - 10.43T_m^2 \tag{37}$$

$$\eta = 0.73 - 4.82T_m - 17.01T_m^2 \tag{38}$$

5. Conclusions

The presented diagnostics method enables determination of parameter values describing static and dynamic properties of the entire solar segment and of a single collector in operating conditions. The provided analyses indicate that based on the recorded time history of solar irradiance and the medium inlet and outlet temperature, it is possible to create, using the parametric identification method, a digital model of the solar segment, equivalent to the analog model developed based on the collector energy

Fig. 11. Impact of the circulating pump capacity on the heat loss coefficient U_{LK} .

balance (HWB equation). The comparison of both models allows for determination of characteristic parameters of the entire solar segment and a single collector. The presented analyses show that the collector static and dynamic properties in operating conditions significantly differ from the parameters determined during standard tests compliant with ISO 9806. The volume flow rate and the collector heat load are important factors that have an impact on the collector static and dynamic properties. Based on the presented results, it shall be concluded that to optimize a solar system efficiency, the medium volume flow rate in the system should be variable. At low temperature in the domestic hot water storage tank, the medium flow rate in the solar system should be maximum. Along with the temperature increase in the domestic hot water storage tank, the flow rate in the solar system should decrease, and at high temperature values in the storage tank, it should be minimum.

Fig. 12. Comparison of static characteristics of the system for three flow rate values with static characteristic made with ISO 9806 standard.

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